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Pen Plotter as a Low-Cost Platform for Rapid Device Prototyping with Solution-Processable Nanomaterials

Gulsum Ersu¹, Yigit Sozen¹, Estrella Sánchez¹, Sruthi Kuriakose¹, Beatriz H. Juárez¹, Federico Mompean¹, Mar Garcia-Hernandez¹, Lea Visscher^{2,3}, Alvaro J. Magdaleno^{2,3}, Ferry Prins^{2,3}, Abdullah M. Al-Enizi⁴, Ayman Nafady⁴, Carmen Munuera¹, Joshua O. Island⁵, Andres Castellanos-Gomez^{1}*

¹ Materials Science Factory. Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC), Madrid, E-28049, Spain

² Condensed Matter Physics Center (IFIMAC), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

³ Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

⁴ Department of Chemistry, College of Science, King Saud University, Riyadh, 11451, Saudi Arabia

⁵ Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Nevada Las Vegas, Las Vegas, NV, 89154, USA

*E-mail: andres.castellanos@csic.es

We propose the use of inexpensive benchtop plotters in combination with refillable writing pens and markers as a powerful route to print nanomaterial-based inks on paper substrates. We prove that this approach is very robust, it can be used to print inks of many different solution-processable nanomaterials, and is very precise, allowing pattern features with pitch separation as narrow as 80 μm . We illustrate the general character of this printing platform by printing van der Waals materials, organic semiconductors, hybrid perovskites and colloidal nanoparticles with a broad range of properties (from insulators to superconductors). We additionally use the system to easily create several example applications such as an all-printed, paper-supported photodetector. This printing platform can be very helpful for research groups with a wealth of expertise in synthesis of solution processable nanomaterials but that lack the infrastructure, resources and expertise to perform traditional inkjet printing for fast device prototyping.

1. Introduction

Recent developments in solution-processable organic semiconductors have unleashed the opportunity to apply the vast knowledge in ink-printing lithographic techniques, optimized over the last five centuries, to fabricate electronic devices quickly and easily.^[1–6] To date, many material families including nanotubes, nanowires, quantum dots (QDs), van der Waals materials,^[7–10] and hybrid perovskites^[11–13] have been isolated in a solution-processable way, broadening the catalog of materials compatible with ink-printing lithographic techniques. Unlike other device fabrication techniques, like electron beam or optical lithography, ink-printing lithographic techniques promise low fabrication costs and unbeatable scale-up possibilities.^[14,15] The combination of solution-processable nanomaterials and ink-printing techniques will be crucial to developing ultra-low-cost electronic components to accommodate the incipient field of ubiquitous electronics.

The most widespread ink-printing lithography methods for fabrication of devices (inkjet printing and spray-coating),^[16–26] however, require rather sophisticated and expensive equipment making the entry-level threshold too high to start producing ink-printed-based devices in many laboratories. This is in striking contrast with the unprecedented low threshold to produce electronic inks with certain nanomaterials that can be easily carried out in labs running on a tight budget.^[7] There have been previous attempts to retrofit standard office printers to allow the printing of nanomaterial-based inks,^[27] with the aim to make it easier to prototype devices with lab-formulated inks without the need for sophisticated material printer systems. This approach, however, requires non-trivial optimization of the prepared inks to avoid printer-injector clogging. For example, we succeeded in printing commercially available PEDOT: PSS ink over a few days in a retrofitted Epson L3151 printer but it ended up clogged, and ultimately unusable.

Motivated by these attempts, we aimed to develop a low-cost, easy and robust technique to print solution-processable inks to allow rapid device prototyping for researchers investigating nanomaterial inks. We show how the use of an inexpensive benchtop pen plotter, in combination with standard stationery writing tools (ballpoint pen, fountain pen, or marker pen), yields a very powerful method to print electronic inks. The pen-plotting method has been proposed as a cost-effective, high-throughput fabrication strategy for paper-based

microanalytical diagnostic devices.^[28–31] This approach was successfully implemented to pattern hydrophobic barriers delineating the hydrophilic reaction zones in paper-based microfluidics, using the as-purchased ink of commercial marker pens. There are also other works re-filling commercially available ballpoint pens with conductive inks like liquid metals or silver-nanoparticles (NPs), carbon nanotubes or MXene inks.^[32–36] In these works, however, the pen-plotted films are mainly used as conductive tracks and very limited functionality was demonstrated. There is a handful of works reported where plotting systems are modified with different inkjet deposition systems to pattern functional materials like organic semiconductors or metal oxides to fabricate transistors or gas sensors. In these works, however, the non-trivial modifications are not discussed in detail enough to allow the easy reproducibility of the system and results by other research groups.^[37–40]

Here, we thoroughly describe the low-cost plotter system and the refillable writing tools employed to pattern films with inks of solution-processable nanomaterials on paper substrates. We show the versatility of this method to print inks that can be applied to different material families (colloidal semiconductor NPs, hybrid perovskites, organic semiconductors and van der Waals materials) independent of their electronic properties (ranging from insulators to superconductors) on paper substrates. We find that tracks with sub-mm width can be reliably patterned with just a $\sim 100\ \mu\text{m}$ track-to-track separation. We illustrate the use of this technique and accompanying tools with different application examples: printing an invisible QR code, coating a paper substrate with a film of high critical temperature superconductor, and fabricating a paper-supported photodetector device.

2. Results and Discussion

Figure 1: Digital photographs of the equipment used for pen plotting: (a) General view of the plotting system, (b) the pen holder, (c-f) images of the ballpoint pen, fountain pen, fine-tip marker, and broad-tip marker pen, respectively.

Figure 1a shows a picture of the inexpensive (<200 €) benchtop plotter (Baugger Plotter, more information given in materials and methods section) used in this work. The system features two raisers equipped with stepper motors to move the loaded pen accurately. The pen holder has a servo motor that controls the height of the pen during the plotting. Figure 1b shows a detailed picture of the pen holder, compatible with different writing tools. In this work, we have tested 3 different kinds of writing tools: ballpoint pen, fountain pen, and

marker pen (details in the materials and methods section). Figure 1c shows a picture of an empty refillable ballpoint pen (Schneider Ballpoint pen) compatible with a fountain pen ink converter. The inset in Figure 1c shows a zoomed-in picture of the ball pen tip. Figure 1d shows a picture of the fountain pen used in this work (Jinhao 599). Figure 1e and 1f show pictures of two different marker pens (empty, refillable, of Magiin brand), one with an extra-fine nib and one with a broad nib.

Figure 2: Digital microscope images of line-space structure drawn with (a) a ballpoint pen, (b) a fountain pen, (c) a fine-tip marker pen, and (d) a broad-tip marker pen filled with water-soluble graphite ink. The right panel shows a digital image of the word 'Merhaba' (Hello in Turkish) drawn with different pens.

We first characterize these different writing tools and the plotter setup with commercially available water-soluble graphite ink (Agar Scientific, Aquadag Graphite, G303E). We plotted a series of parallel lines on standard copy paper (A4, 80 g/m²), reducing the distance between them to find the minimum resolvable feature separation. We have also thoroughly tested the plotting capabilities on kraft paper (170 g/m²), see the Supporting Information, and we have preliminary results on satin textile as well. In general, we believe that this film deposition method can be very robust (almost independently of the rheology of the employed inks) when combined with porous and wettable substrates. Plotting reliable films on other substrates like polymers, glass or SiO₂/Si will require a more thorough optimization of the rheology properties of the inks. For example, we have observed that commercially available silver-loaded ink pens (Circuit Scribe Pen, 1568-1636-ND at DigiKey) can be successfully plotted onto polycarbonate. **Figure 2a-d** shows the results of this characterization process with the ballpoint pen, fountain pen, fine-tip marker, and broad-tip marker, respectively. These images also show the difference in trace (line) width when using the different writing tools, ranging from 0.5 mm for the ballpoint pen and fountain pen to 1.3 mm for the broad-tip marker pen. The ballpoint pen traces are less homogeneous than the ones achieved with the fountain pen or the marker pens. This should be taken into account for applications like electronics that require an uninterrupted conduction path. The narrowest separation between lines ranges from 80 μm to 150 μm. We note that the resolution is limited by the ink spreading on the rough paper surface resulting in the blurriness of the printed lines. Therefore, feature sizes are expected to depend on the characteristics of the ink used, the substrate properties and not limited by the plotter motor resolution. The right side panels in Figure 2 show a comparison of the plotting of the word Merhaba (Hello in Turkish) to give an idea of the aspect of macroscopic print-outs. The text with the lowest line edge roughness is drawn with the marker pens.

Figure 3: Visual comparison of different liquid materials plotted on paper by using a broad-tip marker pen. Photograph of the (a) MoS₂, (b) BSCCO, (c) MoO₃, (d) PEDOT: PSS, (e) MAPbI₃ perovskite and (f) alloyed CdS_xSe_{1-x}/ZnS QD inks on paper.

In the following, we demonstrate the general character of this printing technique with many different solution processable materials. To do so, we filled in a series of broad tip permanent markers with inks of different nanomaterials and performed a test plot. **Figure 3a** to **3c** show the traces achieved with van der Waals-based inks: MoS₂ (Molybdenum disulfide), BSCCO (Bismuth lead strontium calcium copper oxide, Bi_{1.8}Pb_{0.26}Sr₂Ca₂Cu₃O_x), and MoO₃ (molybdenum trioxide) respectively. Interestingly, while the MoO₃ trace is barely distinguishable under visible light, it becomes dark upon UV illumination (365 nm) due to its wide band gap (Figure 3c).^[41,42] Figure 3d shows a trace obtained with an organic semiconductor material (PEDOT: PSS) ink and Figure 3e shows the trace obtained with a marker pen filled with the precursor solution of a hybrid organic-inorganic perovskite

(MAPbI₃). After annealing the substrate on a hot plate (80 °C for 10 min), the plotted MAPbI₃ precursor trace is converted to hybrid perovskite with its characteristic dark brown color. Figure 3f shows a trace using an ink made out of a colloidal CdS_xSe_{1-x}/ZnS alloyed QDs solution. Under UV illumination, the QD trace shows photoluminescence emission (Figure 3f) but with a turquoise blue color that does not match the photoluminescence maxima of the alloyed CdS_xSe_{1-x}/ZnS QDs solution (at 515 nm, not shown). The resulting color is the mixture of the QD emission and the emissive blue response of the paper underneath, which typically yields a strong blue fluorescence emission due to the bleaching treatment to whiten it. See the Supporting Information S1 for an image of clearer and brighter photoluminescence green emission of a QD trace printed on a paper with lower fluorescence background. We have also tested the marker pen + plotter capabilities with a colloidal solution of Ag₂S NPs that emit in the infra-red part of the spectrum (see Supporting Information Figure S2 and Figure S3). We address the reader to the Supporting Information Figure S4 for a scanning electron microscopy characterization of the as-printed films.

We have also characterized the basic electrical properties of printed films of MoS₂, PEDOT, and graphite (See Supporting Information Figures S5-S7) and we have printed graphite films on kraft paper as well (See Figures S8 and S9). In these Supporting Information figures we include statistical analysis of sheet resistance on 400 films of graphite printed on standard office paper and kraft paper.

Figure 4: Applications using our pen plotter system. (a) a MoO_3 based QR (quick response) code that is barely visible under normal illumination conditions but becomes visible upon UV illumination, (b) Responsivity as a function of the incident light power density of a PEDOT:PSS photodetector with graphite electrodes prepared with the pen plotter system (see the inset picture). The inset shows a photocurrent - time curve and a picture of the illuminated device. (c) Magnetization vs. temperature curves of a BSCCO film pen-printed on paper. Red arrows show the two superconductor transition temperatures consistent with BSCCO phases 2212 (near 75 K) and 2223 (near 106 K). Inset shows magnetization vs. magnetic field curves measured at 88 K, 27 K, and 5 K.

Finally, we illustrate the use of the pen plotter with marker pens filled with inks of different nanomaterials in some selected example applications. In fact, the pen-plotter fabricated films still preserve the functional properties of the parent compound, and thus this opens up endless possibilities for devices fabricated with the pen-plotter and pens filled with nanomaterials-based inks. **Figure 4a** shows a digital image of a QR (quick response) code printed on standard paper with the pen-plotter system and a MoO₃ ink filled marker pen. Due to the wide bandgap of MoO₃, the QR code is barely visible under normal visible light but it becomes easily visible when illuminated with UV (365 nm) light. This QR code required less than five minutes to plot and it can be easily scanned with a smartphone.

We have also used the plotter to combine different materials to fabricate functional devices. Figure 4b shows an example of a photodetector made with a PEDOT:PSS channel and graphite electrodes (see inset in Figure 4b). A ~1.5 mm wide PEDOT:PSS trace is made in a first layer with the pen plotter system equipped with a wide-tip marker pen loaded with the PEDOT:PSS ink (vertical light gray line in the inset in Figure 4b), then the marker pen is replaced by a graphite ink loaded one to pattern the graphite electrodes (broad black horizontal lines in the inset in Figure 4b). The device is then tested in a homebuilt probe station supplemented with a lens system to illuminate the device through fiber-coupled LED sources,^[43] operated at ambient conditions. The device displays a responsivity up to 175 μA/W. The inset in Fig 4b shows a current vs. time trace while the illumination is switched ON and OFF, the device response time is around 0.6 s. Figure 4c shows another example where a BSCCO filled marker pen has been used to deposit a thin film of high critical temperature superconductor on paper. A strip of office paper has been covered with a dense film of BSCCO with the pen-plotter. Measurements of the magnetization as a function of temperature showed how the as-printed film displays two clear superconducting transitions corresponding to the 2212 and 2223 BSCCO phases. The magnetization dependence as a function of magnetic field measurements (inset Figure 4c) results in a “diamond” shape hysteresis cycle. This rhomboidal shape is the expected behavior for a Type-II superconductor and the hysteretic behavior is directly related to a non-zero intra-grain superconducting critical current density. Note that the demonstration of a light-sensitive device on paper through the pen-plotting method and the robust high critical temperature

transition also on paper are two illustrative examples that are beyond the current state of the art in the literature.

In summary, we have demonstrated that inexpensive benchtop plotters, in combination with refillable writing tools, are a powerful platform to print inks based on different nanomaterials. We have shown that this ink-printing method is robust, it allows pattern features with pitch separation as narrow as 80 μm and it can be used with a variety of solution processable nanomaterials. We show part of the potential of this technique through a selection of illustrative examples. We believe that this work can be very helpful to labs focused on the synthesis of solution processable nanomaterials that lack the infrastructure and expertise to perform traditional inkjet printing.

3. Materials and Methods

Van der Waals materials:

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS_2 , 99%, Alfa Aesar, 41827), molybdenum trioxide (MoO_3 , 99%, Alfa Aesar, A11159) powder were dispersed in 85:15 v/v ethanol: DI water using bath sonication for 5 min to obtain a well-mixed suspension. 0.1 ml Fairy liquid was added as a surfactant and printable stable suspensions were obtained. Poly(3,4-ethylene dioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT: PSS) conductive polymer was purchased from Aldrich (739316) and used by filling directly into the refillable pen. Graphite ink was prepared by dissolving Aquadag Graphite (Agar, G303E) in DI water (1:1 v/v).

BSCCO powders (Can Superconductors, Ringhofferova 66, 251 68 Kamenice, Czech Republic, <https://www.can-superconductors.com/>), consist of two different phases of chemical composition $(\text{Bi, Pb})_2\text{Sr}_2\text{Ca}_{n-1}\text{Cu}_n\text{O}_{4+2n}$: 2212($n=2$) and 2223($n=3$). The commercial BSCCO powders were liquid phase exfoliated in N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, $\geq 99\%$, Sigma-Aldrich®, 270458) using ultrasonic tip (Xmoonant® ultrasonic probe homogenizer, 24 kHz resonant frequency, 10 mm diameter, 650 W total power) for pulse sonication (60% power, 9 hours total time, 6s on, 2s off). The first residue, centrifuged at 630 \times g, is washed in 2-propanol (IPA, 99.9%, Labbox, PROL-POP). This residue is then dispersed in IPA using bath sonication for 10 min to obtain the homogenous dispersion used for the BSCCO ink.

Hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites:

MAPbI₃ Perovskite precursor solutions were prepared by mixing MAI (>99.99%, Greatcell Solar Materials: MS101000-10) and PbI₂ (99.999%, Sigma Aldrich: 203602-50G) with stoichiometric ratios (1:1). Subsequently, the precursor salts were dissolved in DMF (99.8%, anhydrous, Sigma Aldrich: 227056-1L) by stirring at room temperature during 2 h approximately.

Colloidal semiconducting quantum dots:

Cadmium oxide (CdO, 99.99%), sulfur (99.9%, powder), trioctylphosphine (TOP, 97%), oleic acid (OA, technical grade 90%), 1-octadecene (ODE, technical grade 90%), 1-dodecanethiol (DDT, >98%), silver diethyldithiocarbamate (AgDDTC, 99%), chloroform (ACS basic stabilized with ethanol), toluene (99.7%) and ethanol (absolute, Emplura), were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Selenium (99.999%, powder 200 mesh) was purchased from Alfa Aesar. Zinc stearate dihydrate (extra pure) from Sharlab. Acetone (99%) was purchased from Panreac. All chemicals were used directly without further purification.

Alloyed CdS_xSe_{1-x}/ZnS QDs were synthesized by a hot-injection method in Schlenk line according to previous work with slight modifications.^[44] Briefly, 0.05 mmol of CdO and 2 mmol of zinc stearate dihydrate were placed in a 50 mL three-necked round flask, with 2.5 mL of OA. The mixture was heated to 150 °C and degassed for 30 min. Afterwards, 7.5 mL of ODE were added, and the solution was further heated to 300 °C under N₂ atmosphere. At this temperature, a clear solution was observed containing Cd(OA)₂ and Zn(OA)₂ complexes. When the temperature is stabilized, 1 mL of a previously prepared solution containing 0.2 mmol of Se and 1.4 mmol of S in TOP was quickly injected. The QDs were grown for 3 min. After this time, the flask was cooled, and 1.5 mL of DDT were added to the solution. For the purification, two cycles of centrifugation with acetone (precipitation) and dispersion in chloroform were carried out. The final QD-inks contain QDs in chloroform. This solution was used for the refillable marker pens.

Ag₂S NPs were synthesized following previous work with modifications.^[45] The reaction proceeds in Schlenk line in air. For the heat-decomposition reaction, 0.05 mmol of AgDDTC and 12.5 mmol of DDT were mixed in a three-neck round bottom flask and heated to 200 °C for 1 hour and then cooled down to room temperature. At 70° C, 2 mL of toluene were added.

The black colloidal solution was washed in several cycles of precipitation with ethanol and re-dispersion in toluene. The final NP-inks contain Ag₂S NPs in toluene. This solution was used for the refillable marker pens.

Plotting system: A Baugger desktop Plotter machine was used for pen-printing plotting. We used the provided control software to load and vectorize black and white raster images with the desired pattern to be pen-printed. We found that printing speeds of 300 mm/min to 1200 mm/min provided good trace quality and that the actual optimal speed depends on the viscosity of the used ink. We measured an applied force of 1.2 N during the drawing process. The drawing was performed using different refillable pens (Schneider ballpoint pen, Jinhao 599 fountain pen, and Magiin empty refillable marker pen) and inks. About 2 mL of ink solution was loaded into the empty pens and then the pens were installed into the plotter. After printing, the substrates were dried in ambient conditions and the images were acquired using a Canon EOS 1200D digital SLR camera.

Magnetic characterization:

The magnetic measurements of the thin film of BSCCO on paper were performed with a Quantum Design® PPMS 9 Tesla system equipped with a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM). Magnetization (M) vs. temperature (T) curves were measured cooling from room temperature to 10 K under an applied magnetic field (H) of 50 Oe. Hysteresis cycles (*i.e.* M vs. H scans) were measured at constant temperatures of 5 K, 27 K and 88 K, starting from zero field cooled samples.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information:

Pen Plotter as a Low-Cost Platform for Rapid Device Prototyping with Solution-Processable Nanomaterials

Gulsum Esru¹, Yigit Sozen¹, Estrella Sánchez¹, Sruthi Kuriakose¹, Beatriz H. Juárez¹, Federico Mompean¹, Mar Garcia-Hernandez¹, Lea Visscher^{2,3}, Alvaro J. Magdaleno^{2,3}, Ferry Prins^{2,3}, Abdullah M. Al-Enizi⁴, Ayman Nafady⁴, Carmen Munuera¹, Joshua O. Island⁵, Andres Castellanos-Gomez¹

¹ Materials Science Factory. Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC), Madrid, E-28049, Spain

² Condensed Matter Physics Center (IFIMAC), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

³ Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain.

⁴ Department of Chemistry, College of Science, King Saud University, Riyadh, 11451, Saudi Arabia

⁵ Department of Physics and Astronomy, University of Nevada Las Vegas, Las Vegas, NV, 89154, USA

Figure S1: Alloyed $\text{CdS}_x\text{Se}_{1-x}/\text{ZnS}$ QD ink plotted on drawing paper with a low fluorescence background.

Figure S2: Ink based on a colloidal suspension of Ag_2S in toluene plotted onto paper. (a) low concentration of NPs in the ink. The trace is invisible with visible light (left) but it emits IR photoluminescence that can be seen with an IR camera. (b) Similar experiment but with an ink of higher concentration where the trace can be seen now in the visible.

Figure S3: Example of QR code plotted onto paper with the ink based on a colloidal suspension of Ag_2S NPs in toluene. The pattern shows IR photoluminescence that can be seen with an IR camera.

Figure S4: SEM images of the different as-printed films on paper: Graphite, MoS₂, MoO₃, PEDOT: PSS, Perovskite, and Quantum dot.

Figure S4 shows some scanning electron microscopy images of plotted films on standard office copy paper. For the van der Waals materials (graphite, MoS₂ and MoO₃) one can distinguish

the structure of the film composed of a network of interconnected flakes. The commercially available graphite ink is composed by very small graphite flakes (sub micrometer lateral dimensions). The MoS₂ ink, made by liquid phase exfoliation, is composed by much bigger flakes (1-20 μm range) and the MoO₃ is composed of flakes in the 1-5 μm range. The lateral size of the flakes composing the inks can be controlled through the selection of the initial van der Waals powders, the liquid phase exfoliation parameters, the solvent and the use of centrifugation size-selection. Our MoS₂ ink is not optimized at all and yet we managed to get electrical conduction (see Figure below). For the rest of the materials, as expected, it is difficult to observe any microscopic feature besides the fact that the cellulose fibers are indeed covered with a film.

Figure S5: The electrical characterization of various inks on paper. (a) The two-terminal resistance is plotted as a function of the length between the electrodes and (b) a picture of a device with the silver electrode and MoS₂, PEDOT:PSS, and graphite ink channel, respectively.

Figure S6: Sheet resistance statistics of graphite ink films on standard office paper. 400 graphite films on standard office paper has been prepared with the plotter and their sheet resistance has been measured in 4-terminal configuration (Ossila 4-point probe, T2001A3).

Figure S7: Resistivity statistics of graphite ink films on standard office paper assuming an average thickness of the graphite film of $\sim 20\ \mu\text{m}$. 400 graphite films on standard office paper has been prepared with the plotter and their sheet resistance has been measured in 4-terminal configuration. The resistivity has been calculated by assuming a thickness of $\sim 20\ \mu\text{m}$, obtained from the analysis of cross-section images on a graphite ink-based film at six different locations.

Figure S8: Sheet resistance statistics of graphite ink films on kraft paper. 400 graphite films on kraft paper has been prepared with the plotter and their sheet resistance has been measured in 4-terminal configuration (Ossila 4-point probe, T2001A3).

Figure S9: Resistivity statistics of graphite ink films on standard kraft paper assuming an average thickness of the graphite film of ~40 μm . 400 graphite films on kraft paper has been prepared with the plotter and their sheet resistance has been measured in 4-terminal configuration. The resistivity has been calculated by assuming a thickness of ~40 μm , obtained from the analysis of a cross-section image of a graphite ink film on Kraft paper, analyzing the thickness at six different locations.